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SITUATION AND SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE WORK PHYSICAL EDUCATION FOR TEACHING STUDENTS NORTHWEST UNIVERSITY

Abstract. Physical education at the University of Northwest is concerned by the school's management. However, there are limitations and weaknesses that require specific solutions to develop and improve physical education.

Keywords: Actual situation of physical education, solutions and improvement of physical education, physical education of pedagogical students.

1. Question

Northwestern University with a long history, with the goal of training human resources for the Northwest region and surrounding areas. The school always pays close attention to the quality of human resources that the school trains, especially physical education. The school has established the Department of Physical Education and Sports with a source of highly qualified young staff to undertake the teaching of physical education for students of the whole school, besides, the Department of Physical Education and Sports has accumulated actively cooperate with the school to invest in facilities, innovate the curriculum in the direction of maximizing the ability of students in the school. With the attention, direction and investment of the government and schools, physical education work has made an encouraging development, contributing positively to the overall achievement in the cause of education and training.

However, besides the achievements, in general, physical education work has many limitations and weaknesses: The quality is not high, the educational effectiveness is limited, and it has not met the current requirements. The number of lecturers sent for higher training is still small, the facilities are still poor, the program, the reference textbooks, the teaching methods, the management work is still slow to innovate, and the sports achievements of the house are still small. school is low.

2. Current status and results of physical education work at Northwestern University

2.1. Organization of management and sports activities

The school bases on the documents and directives of the Ministry of Education and Training on physical education and especially the circular to implement the directive 15/2002/CT-TT of the Prime Minister on anti- negative in sports activities. Directive 12/2005/CT-BGDĐT dated 07/04/2005 on strengthening physical education and school sports movement.

Physical education is a common task of the faculty, under the general direction of the Board of Directors, the Training Department, and all other departments in the school. Therefore, the purpose and mission of physical education has been carried out under the unified leadership of the Faculty and Department, with the close coordination of all lecturers and other departments in the school.

The faculty's leadership firmly grasps the Party's comprehensive educational policy, strictly and creatively abides by the directives and regulations of the Party, the Ministry of Education and Training, and the branch on physical education work.

The school has established a legal inspection department, which is responsible for regularly checking the quality of classroom hours, especially intra-curricular physical education classes and organizing physical training for students.

Faculty leaders always help and suggest ideas for lecturers in the Faculty to improve teaching methods and constantly improve their professional and political qualifications.

The school has established sports clubs, committees responsible for physical training and sports: Organizing and planning physical and sports activities, operating all physical training activities. sports of the faculties and the whole school.

2.2. Status of physical education program at Northwestern University Through the actual survey research at the school, the school has implemented teaching according to the newly improved program, including two physical education modules, 1 is compulsory and physical education is many elective sports as follows: (see Table 1).

Order	Course code	Course name	Number of credits	Credit Type				Prerequisites
				Go to class				
				Theory	Exercise	Essay	Practice	
Basic knowledge block			1					
1	PHE0001	Physical Education 1	1				30	30
Elective knowledge block								

2		Physical Education 2	Students choose one of the courses below						
2.1	PHE0002	Run 100m					60	60	
2.2	PHE0003	Jump far					60	60	
2.3	PHE0004	Volleyball					60	60	
2.4	PHE0005	Aerobics					60	60	
2.5	PHE0006	Sports dance					60	60	
2.6	PHE0007	Football					60	60	
2.7	PHE0008	Taekwondo					60	60	

Table 1: Contents of physical education program

From the table above, it can be seen that the number of subjects belonging to the elective knowledge block is rich but not suitable for the characteristics of the school's students, because most of the students are children of the Northwestern ethnic groups and Lao students are studying abroad. attend school. Especially pedagogical students.

2.3. Facilities for physical education work

Because the school is in the process of construction and completion, the facilities for teaching and learning still face many difficulties (see Table 2).

Order	Yard, tools	Quantity	Quality	Evaluate
1	Football pitches	1	Good	Obtain
2	Volleyball yard	3	Medium	Obtain
3	100m running track	2	Medium	Obtain
4	Long jump hole	2	Medium	Obtain
5	Single bar	3	Medium	Obtain
6	Double beams	3	Medium	Obtain
7	skewed beams	2	Medium	Obtain
8	Gymnasiums	0		
9	Stadium	0		

Table 2: Actual situation of yards and facilities for teaching and training

Although the school has tried its best, there are still many difficulties, inadequacies and limitations such as: The lack of facilities and low quality, thus affecting the quality of physical education in the school.

2.4. About the teaching staff

Northwestern University has established the Department of Physical Education and Sports - Faculties Faculty, which is responsible for teaching in all faculties of the university.

The total number of lecturers of the Department of Physical Education and Sports is currently 22 lecturers. Meeting the requirements and tasks, especially conducting physical education according to the new training program (see Table 3).

Order	total N = 22		Quantity
1	Level	College	0
		University	0
		Master	16
		Doctor	6
2	Seniority (years)	Over 10 years	17
		Less than 10 years	5
3	Specialize	Athletics	5
		Exercise	1
		Sports management	1
		Medicine	1
		Volleyball	5
		Taekwondo	2
		Handball	1
		Badminton	2
		Basketball	1
		Football	3
		4	Sex
Female	5		

Table 3: Quality of lecturers of Physical Education and Sports Department – Faculties of Northwestern University

The training, fostering to improve the professional skills of lecturers in the faculty is paid great attention by the school, encouraged, encouraged and created all conditions for them to study and improve their qualifications. Therefore, the qualifications of lecturers in the faculty have also been raised according to the new requirements of the Ministry of Education and Training. The increasing life of lecturers is also a driving force for lecturers to feel secure in their work and consciously advance in teaching and scientific research. This is the most decisive factor to the development of physical education in schools in the following years.

2.5. Physical fitness of pedagogical students

Based on the standards of physical fitness assessment according to Decision No. 53/2008/QD-BGDDT dated September 18, 2008 of the Minister of Education and Training on the assessment and classification of students' physical fitness. We surveyed and classified the physical health of students K62 and K63 of Northwestern University with a total of 967 students as follows (see Table 4). [5]

Order	Sex	Classify		
		Good	Obtain	Not reached
1	Nam (n=233)	175 (75,11%)	26 (11,16%)	32 (13,73%)

2	Nĩr (n=734)	566 (77,11%)	103 (14,03%)	65 (8,86%)
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Table 4: Survey results and student health classification K62, K63 (n = 967)

Thus, the problem of students' physical health is not equal, the percentage of students with weak physical strength accounts for quite high (11.2%). This is an issue that physical education needs to pay attention to in order to minimize the number of students with weak physical strength.

3. Some solutions to improve the quality of physical education work at Northwestern University [2], [6]

In order to improve the training quality of the school and consolidate and improve the direction, management, physical education and sports movement to meet the needs of students and society, we I suggest the following specific solutions:

Solution 1. Together with organizations and unions in the school, promote forms of educational propaganda, raising students' awareness of the effects and effectiveness of physical training and sports and the benefits of exercise. sport.

Solution 2. Improve the content of physical training and sports, establish a Board of Directors with specialized sub-committees, organize classes and sports teams, streamline and strengthen lecturers and guides. members in activities. The Board of Directors, the Trade Union, the Youth Union, and the Student Union appoint representatives to participate in directing and managing the organization of activities.

Solution 3. Invest in renovating and upgrading and equipping more facilities and exercise equipment.

The school needs to combine more investment sources from individuals who are officials and employees of the school to have funding for the operation. Cooperate with other departments to have a more fully supported investment source.

Solution 4. Work closely with the Youth Union, Student Union, and sport instructors to maintain the practice routine. Selecting and fostering guides who are students, officials and lecturers in the school, especially students who are school-going staff. Developing the most number of students is the 1st, 2nd and 3rd year students.

Solution 5. Make regular plans to organize competitions, performances, friendly sports inside and outside the school according to the celebrations in the school. Select and train the team to participate in sports tournaments of superiors.

Solution 6. Praise, encourage and reward students with sports achievements in a timely manner. There are specific plans on training, competition and reward regimes for athletes who are students of the school when participating in sports competitions of all levels.

4. Conclude

From the results obtained during the research we can conclude that:

- The reality of physical education work at Northwestern University is basically satisfactory in terms of teaching expertise. But the management apparatus has many limitations that have to go through many departments and there is no consensus. The physical facilities for physical education are still lacking in quantity and quality, not guaranteed, and there is no focus investment. The program of internal and external activities is not rich and suitable for students.

- The proposed solutions are very suitable with the current situation of physical education work at schools. Solutions need to be concerned by the Board of Directors and departments to create conditions for physical education activities to bring into full play the purpose and meaning of this activity.

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